

Consistency of yield and yield components from several soybean genotypes in lowland and upland

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ABSTRACT

In Indonesia, soybean is cultivated in upland (at the beginning of the wet and dry season) and lowland (at the beginning of the dry season and during the dry season). The aim of the research was to evaluate the yield and yield components of soybean genotypes in lowland and upland. A total of 16 soybean genotypes (including Anjasmoro and Grobogan as check varieties) were evaluated in two locations in upland (Blitar and Pasuruan) and two locations in lowland (Banyuwangi and Nganjuk). The experiment in each location was arranged in a randomized block design with four replications. The average yields in the upland of Blitar and Pasuruan were 2.70 t/ha and 2.51 t/ha, respectively. The average yields in the lowland of Banyuwangi and Nganjuk were 2.51 t/ha and 3.03 t/ha, respectively. The difference of average yield between lowland (2.77 t/ha) and upland (2.61 t/ha) was 0.61 t/ha. Days to maturity was not affected by a different type of land area. The average number of the filled pod in upland (45.41 pods/plant) was higher than those of in lowland (42.82 pods/plant). On the contrary, the number of empty pods in upland (2.49 pods/plant) was higher than in lowland (1.68 pods/plant). Interestingly, the average seed size in upland (17.41 g/100 seed) was higher than those of in lowland (16.24 g/100 seed). This fact showed that soybean can be developed both of upland and lowland. The difference in seed yield was more caused by the potential genetic differential of each genotype. High yielding genotype in lowland is also likely to produce a high yield in upland, and vice versa. Soybean genotypes UAK-15-6-7 and UAK-15-1-4-2 were identified as adaptable to both upland and lowland, and their agronomic characteristics were in accordance with the soybean preferences in Indonesia, i.e. early maturity and large seed size.

Key words: seed yield, yield component, lowland, upland

INTRODUCTION

The agroecosystem of Indonesia is unique in the terms of soybean cultivation and development. The growing season in Indonesia is divided into three groups, namely the beginning of the rainy season (November/December - February/March), the beginning of the dry season (February/March - May/June) and the dry season (June/July - September/October). Soybean cultivation can be

conducted in dry land, at the beginning of the rainy season or the beginning of the dry season, and also in paddy fields at the beginning of the dry season and in the dry season. The development of soybean in an area could be done in dry land or in paddy fields. With such conditions, it is necessary to provide soybean varieties that are not only adaptive to paddy fields but also able to have high production in the dry land.

The adaptability of a soybean genotype in various environments is a complex factor. This is due to the interaction between genotypes and environment (Alghamdi 2004; Arsyad & Nur 2006; Krisnawati & Adie 2008; Jandong et al., 2011), which indicates the specific adaptation for each genotype. Various studies showed that the role of the environment was greater than the role of the genotype in determining the performance of seed yields. Krisnawati & Adie (2018) conducted an evaluation in eight soybean production centers in Indonesia and obtained the environment contributed 64.4% in determining grain yields, followed by the role of genotypes and interactions between genotypes and the environment (10.8% and 24.8%, respectively).

In the field pea (*Pisum sativum* L.), the effect of the environment was 79.68%, and greater than the effects of the genotype and G×E (4.53% and 5.70%, respectively) when evaluated in 12 environments (Fikere et al. 2009). This indicates that different growing environments will affect the variation of seed yields between genotypes. Ashraf (2010) identified the environment as an important factor (95.80%) in determining soybean yield compared to the role of genotype and G×E which only contributed 80.84% and 60.86%, respectively. The performance of seed yield of a variety, especially on the scale of cultivation by farmers, is determined by the factors of G × E × M (genetic, environmental and management).

Facts in the field indicates that a low yield of soybean seeds is mostly caused by environmental and management factors. Tyagi and Khan (2013) evaluated the seed yield of 40 soybean genotypes in eight locations in India, and successfully identified the most determining environmental factors were soil treatment and nitrogen fertilization. Research in Turkey conducted by Karasu et al. (2009) did not obtain soybean genotype with stable yield, but were able to define the adaptability of each genotype in optimal and sub-optimal environments.

The interesting thing that soybean cultivation which conducted in several agro-ecosystems has an impact on seed supply systems through the distribution of seed production between locations and between seasons. In such conditions, the provision of adaptive soybean varieties in the lowland and dry land, is requires continuity production for both consumption and seed purposes. Yursak & Purwantoro (2013) reported that Wilis, Anjasmoro,

Argomulyo and Burangrang varieties were adaptable to upland and dry land agroecosystems. Bahar & Chairunas (2012) studied the adaptation of several soybean varieties at different locations and concluded that Anjasmoro and Kipas Merah varieties were adaptive to be developed in Pidie and Bireuen (Aceh, Indonesia).

The aim of the research was to evaluate the yield and yield components of soybean genotypes in lowland and upland

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research materials were 16 soybean genotypes, which consisted of 14 lines and two check varieties of Anjasmoro (medium maturity and large seeded-size) and Grobogan (early maturity and large seeded-size). The experiments were carried out in upland (Blitar and Pasuruan) and lowland (Banyuwangi and Nganjuk). The experiment in each location was arranged in a randomized block design with four replications. The field experiment at in upland was conducted in the end of the rainy season (January to April), and in the lowland was conducted at the beginning of the dry season (February to May).

The research on each location was arranged in a randomly block design. The treatment was 16 soybean genotypes with four replicates. Each genotype was planted by tugal planting system on a 2.4 m ×4.5 m plot size and 40 cm × 15 cm planting distance. Plants were fertilized by 250 kg Phonska/ha + 100 kg SP 36 and 1 t/ha organic fertilizer, which applied entirely after sowing the seeds. In lowland paddy field after rice planting was under zero tillage condition, and irrigation channel was made before planting. The weed was controlled two and four weeks after planting.

The observed data were days to maturity, plant height, number of branches, number of nodes, number of filled pod, number of empty pod, 100 seed weight, and seed yield. Data were analyzed using combined analysis of variance (ANOVA).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Combined analysis of variance

The combined analysis of variance for yield and yield components of 16 soybean genotypes in four locations was presented in Table 1. Location and genotype were significant for all characters studied. There were significant interaction between genotype with location (GEI) for characters of plant height, 100 seed weight, and seed yield. The significant GEI showed that the performance of plant height, 100 seed weight, and seed yield were determined by the location

and the genetic differences among genotypes. The CV value ranged from 2.06 to 34.88%.

Table 1. Combined analysis of variance of yield and yield components

No	Character	Mean square			CV (%)
		Location (E)	Genotype (G)	G × E	
1	Days to maturity (days)	0.0001 **	47.1958 **	0.0001 ns	2.06
2	Plant height (cm)	5925.1914 **	1316.8262 **	178.5714 **	10.58
3	Number of node/plant	96.2184 **	44.1599 **	9.5128 ns	22.89
4	Number of filled pod/plant	3590.8716 **	308.8077 **	164.2023 ns	25.74
5	Number of empty pod/plant	31.4867 **	4.8538 **	1.3371 ns	33.44
6	100 seed weight (g)	112.8144 **	29.0269 **	4.8389 **	7.27
7	Seed yield (t/ha)	6.9371 **	0.7310 **	0.4517 **	13.58

= significant at 1 % probability level ($p < 0.01$), ns = not significant, CV = coefficient of variation **Seed yield

Seed yield

The average seed yield of upland and lowland were 2.51 t/ha and 2.77 t/ha, respectively. There was 5.77% yield increase of soybean yield in lowland compared to upland (Table 2). The seed yield in upland of Blitar and Pasuruan were 2.70 and 2.51 t/ha, respectively. Yield productivity at Blitar location was higher than in Pasuruan. In lowland, Nganjuk's location (3.03 t/ha) was more productive than Banyuwangi (2.51 t/ha).

The range of yield in upland was 2.21 – 3.00 t/ha and in lowland was 2.33 – 3.23 t/ha. The range of seed yield of five best genotypes in upland was 2.81 – 3.00 t/ha and five best genotypes in lowland ranged from 2.97 – 3.03 t/ha. According to Mohammadi et al. (2015), genotype which showed consistently high yield across location was considered as a stable genotype. If combining the five best genotypes from both of upland and lowland, then there are two soybean genotypes, namely UAK-15-6-7 and UAK-15-1-4-2, showed consistent high yield in these two types of land. This shows that both soybean genotypes are able to produce high yields in both upland and lowland.

The UAK-15-11-2 genotype was able to produce 3.00 t/ha in upland, but it was produce only 2.74 t/ha when cultivated in lowland. On the contrary, the UAK-15-1-4 genotype produce 2.95 t/ha in lowland, and only 2.74 t/ha in upland. It means that both genotypes have each specific adaptation, which is only lowland or upland.

Table 2. Seed yield of 16 soybean genotypes in lowland and upland

No	Genotype	Seed yield (t/ha)						Grand average
		Upland			Lowland			
		Blitar	Pasuruan	Average	Banyuwangi	Nganjuk	Average	
1	UAK-15-11-2	3.41	2.60	3.00 (1)	2.60	2.88	2.74	2.87 (4)
2	UAK-15-1-6	2.79	2.90	2.85 (3)	2.90	2.89	2.90	2.87 (4)
3	UAK-15-7-1	2.27	2.60	2.43	2.60	2.74	2.67	2.55
4	UAK-15-5-1	2.09	2.96	2.53	2.96	3.23	3.10 (3)	2.81
5	UAK-15-2-1	3.19	1.73	2.46	1.73	3.12	2.43	2.44
6	UAK-15-1-4	2.54	2.94	2.74	2.94	3.39	3.17 (2)	2.95 (3)
7	UAK-15-1-2	2.77	2.78	2.77	2.78	3.14	2.96	2.87 (4)
8	UAK-15-2-8	3.16	2.46	2.81 (5)	2.46	2.71	2.59	2.70
9	UAK-15-12-15	2.87	2.70	2.78	2.70	2.98	2.84	2.81
10	UAK-15-6-3	2.16	2.26	2.21	2.26	2.52	2.39	2.30
11	UAK-15-19-7	2.49	2.93	2.71	2.93	3.01	2.97 (5)	2.84 (5)
12	UAK-15-1-7	2.07	1.98	2.02	1.98	3.10	2.54	2.28
13	UAK-15-6-7	3.50	2.43	2.96 (2)	2.43	3.70	3.07 (4)	3.01 (2)
14	UAK-15-1-4-2	2.96	2.73	2.84 (4)	2.73	3.72	3.23 (1)	3.03 (1)
15	Anjasmoro	2.53	1.91	2.22	1.91	2.75	2.33	2.28
16	Grobogan	2.49	2.26	2.38	2.26	2.65	2.46	2.42
Average		2.70	2.51	2.61	2.51	3.03	2.77	2.69

(...) = best rank from 1 to 5

Days to maturity and seed size

The preferences of farmers and soybean industry in Indonesia are focused on three characters, namely high yield, early maturity (<80 days) and large seed size (>14 g/100 seed). The average of days to maturity on two types of land was 78 days. The days to maturity in both upland and lowland were not significantly different due to similar environmental conditions.

The days to maturity in upland ranged from 75 – 82 days, and in lowland ranged from 76 – 82 hari (Table 3). This shows that all tested genotypes were categorized as early maturity except Anjasmoro (medium maturity, 82 days). Based on this research, there was no genotypes which has comparable maturity with Grobogan variety.

Soybean large seeded size is important as raw material for tempeh industry in Indonesia. The average soybean seed size in upland (17.41 g/100 seed) was higher than in lowland (16.24 g/100 seed). All genotypes have large seed size (> 14 g/100 seed), both in upland and lowland. Grobogan variety have the largest seed size, both in upland and lowland, and there was no genotypes with seed size over the Grobogan variety.

Table 3. Days to maturity of 16 soybean genotypes in lowland and upland

No	Genotype	Maturity day					Grand average	
		Upland			Lowland			
		Blitar	Pasuruan	Average	Banyuwangi	Nganjuk		Average
1	UAK-15-11-2	76	78	77	78	80	79	78
2	UAK-15-1-6	77	77	77	77	78	78	77
3	UAK-15-7-1	77	76	76	76	76	76	76
4	UAK-15-5-1	80	77	79	77	79	78	79
5	UAK-15-2-1	80	78	79	78	80	79	79
6	UAK-15-1-4	78	78	78	78	80	79	79
7	UAK-15-1-2	80	77	79	77	79	78	79
8	UAK-15-2-8	76	76	76	76	77	77	76
9	UAK-15-12-15	75	76	76	76	76	76	76
10	UAK-15-6-3	80	78	79	78	81	80	79
11	UAK-15-19-7	75	77	76	77	79	78	77
12	UAK-15-1-7	80	78	79	78	80	79	79
13	UAK-15-6-7	82	78	80	78	80	79	80
14	UAK-15-1-4-2	78	77	78	77	79	78	78
15	Anjasmoro	82	82	82	82	82	82	82
16	Grobogan	75	76	75	76	76	76	76
	Average	78	77	78	77	79	78	78

Table 4.100 seeds weight of 16 soybean genotypes in lowland and upland

No	Genotype	100 seeds weight					Grand average	
		Upland			Lowland			
		Blitar	Pasuruan	Average	Banyuwangi	Nganjuk		Average
1	UAK-15-11-2	18.77	15.21	16.99	15.21	15.49	15.35	16.17
2	UAK-15-1-6	21.02	16.22	18.62	16.22	16.85	16.54	17.58
3	UAK-15-7-1	19.26	15.73	17.49	15.73	15.37	15.55	16.52
4	UAK-15-5-1	20.48	15.87	18.17	15.87	16.62	16.25	17.21
5	UAK-15-2-1	16.76	16.42	16.59	16.42	15.52	15.97	16.28
6	UAK-15-1-4	18.80	15.97	17.38	15.97	15.77	15.87	16.63
7	UAK-15-1-2	15.68	15.65	15.66	15.65	15.41	15.53	15.60
8	UAK-15-2-8	20.97	15.93	18.45	15.93	19.20	17.57	18.01
9	UAK-15-12-15	18.94	15.79	17.36	15.79	18.16	16.98	17.17
10	UAK-15-6-3	18.03	15.70	16.86	15.70	15.50	15.60	16.23
11	UAK-15-19-7	18.69	16.18	17.44	16.18	15.95	16.07	16.75
12	UAK-15-1-7	19.48	16.32	17.90	16.32	15.79	16.06	16.98
13	UAK-15-6-7	17.44	15.48	16.46	15.48	16.44	15.96	16.21
14	UAK-15-1-4-2	16.06	15.66	15.86	15.66	14.84	15.25	15.56
15	Anjasmoro	17.19	15.44	16.31	15.44	15.59	15.52	15.91
16	Grobogan	25.37	16.66	21.01	16.66	22.79	19.73	20.37
	Average	18.93	15.89	17.41	15.89	16.58	16.24	16.82

Plant height and number of node

The performance of plant height differs between upland and lowland, whereas the number of node among those two land types was not significant. The average plant height in upland lowland were 67.34 cm and 66.22 cm,

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respectively. Number of node in upland ranged from 11.75 to 18.41 nodes/plant. The UAK-15-1-2 genotype showed the highest number of nodes in upland, whereas the UAK-15-6-7 genotype showed the highest number of nodes in lowland (Table 5 and Table 6).

Table 5. Plant height of 16 soybean genotypes in lowland and upland

No	Genotype	Plant height						Grand average
		Upland			Lowland			
		Blitar	Pasuruan	Average	Banyuwangi	Nganjuk	Average	
1	UAK-15-11-2	58.67	48.45	53.56	48.45	57.42	52.94	53.25
2	UAK-15-1-6	83.08	61.35	72.22	61.35	59.08	60.22	66.22
3	UAK-15-7-1	54.42	47.20	50.81	47.20	43.83	45.52	48.16
4	UAK-15-5-1	77.50	52.20	64.85	52.20	81.42	66.81	65.83
5	UAK-15-2-1	91.00	66.75	78.88	66.75	78.42	72.59	75.73
6	UAK-15-1-4	71.17	68.10	69.63	68.10	59.58	63.84	66.74
7	UAK-15-1-2	86.33	71.55	78.94	71.55	71.50	71.53	75.23
8	UAK-15-2-8	59.34	44.00	51.67	44.00	50.08	47.04	49.36
9	UAK-15-12-15	72.34	54.45	63.39	54.45	60.83	57.64	60.52
10	UAK-15-6-3	82.59	48.75	65.67	48.75	77.17	62.96	64.32
11	UAK-15-19-7	73.42	57.30	65.36	57.30	58.33	57.82	61.59
12	UAK-15-1-7	89.42	49.10	69.26	49.10	75.42	62.26	65.76
13	UAK-15-6-7	94.25	71.40	82.82	71.40	76.08	73.74	78.28
14	UAK-15-1-4-2	92.08	58.00	75.04	58.00	74.50	66.25	70.65
15	Anjasmoro	91.92	64.45	78.18	64.45	74.17	69.31	73.75
16	Grobogan	64.33	50.00	57.17	50.00	61.67	55.84	56.50
Average		77.61	57.07	67.34	57.07	66.22	61.65	64.49

Table 6. Number of node of 16 soybean genotypes in lowland and upland

No	Genotype	Number of node/plant						Grand average
		Upland			Lowland			
		Blitar	Pasuruan	Average	Banyuwangi	Nganjuk	Average	
1	UAK-15-11-2	16.17	12.05	14.11	12.05	13.42	12.74	13.42
2	UAK-15-1-6	16.17	11.75	13.96	11.75	12.50	12.13	13.04
3	UAK-15-7-1	11.84	10.95	11.39	10.95	10.33	10.64	11.02
4	UAK-15-5-1	13.50	12.00	12.75	12.00	16.08	14.04	13.40
5	UAK-15-2-1	15.75	16.85	16.30	16.85	14.58	15.72	16.01
6	UAK-15-1-4	15.67	14.70	15.18	14.70	13.00	13.85	14.52
7	UAK-15-1-2	20.42	16.40	18.41	16.40	13.42	14.91	16.66
8	UAK-15-2-8	15.59	14.00	14.79	14.00	13.50	13.75	14.27
9	UAK-15-12-15	14.67	12.15	13.41	12.15	13.83	12.99	13.20
10	UAK-15-6-3	12.50	11.00	11.75	11.00	16.42	13.71	12.73
11	UAK-15-19-7	15.92	11.70	13.81	11.70	13.33	12.52	13.16
12	UAK-15-1-7	15.75	10.20	12.98	10.20	13.42	11.81	12.40
13	UAK-15-6-7	17.75	14.70	16.23	14.70	17.33	16.02	16.12
14	UAK-15-1-4-2	17.17	14.85	16.01	14.85	16.75	15.80	15.91
15	Anjasmoro	17.75	14.70	16.22	14.70	13.83	14.27	15.24
16	Grobogan	12.67	10.95	11.81	10.95	12.67	11.81	11.81
Average		15.58	13.06	14.32	13.06	14.03	13.55	13.93

The higher the plant will stimulate the increasing number of fertile nodes. The character of fertile nodes is a node in which pods are located, thus the higher of the plants,, hence likely to increase the number of pods.

Number of filled and empty pods

Number of pod was not significantly affected by land types, but it more affected by the difference in the genetic potential of each genotype. The average of filled pod in upland and lowland were 45.41 pods and 42.82 pods, respectively. The number of empty pods in upland was 2.49 pods per plant, whereas in lowland was 1.68 pods per plant (Table7, Table 8).

The UAK-15-1-2 genotype has the highest number of filled pods in upland (57.86 filled pods/plant), whereas UAK-15-2-1 showed the highest number of filled pods in lowland (53.33 pods/plant). When observed the pod distribution, it seems that the more number of filled pods/plants will be followed by the increasing number of empty pods/plants

Table 7.Number of filled pod of 16 soybean genotypes in lowland and upland

No	Genotype	No of filled pod/plant						Grand average
		Upland			Lowland			
		Blitar	Pasuruan	Average	Banyuwangi	Nganjuk	Average	
1	UAK-15-11-2	67.92	37.65	52.78	37.65	45.25	41.45	47.12
2	UAK-15-1-6	50.59	32.15	41.37	32.15	38.25	35.20	38.29
3	UAK-15-7-1	47.42	37.00	42.21	37.00	44.50	40.75	41.48
4	UAK-15-5-1	41.50	35.50	38.50	35.50	49.50	42.50	40.50
5	UAK-15-2-1	54.34	50.75	52.54	50.75	57.50	54.13	53.33
6	UAK-15-1-4	64.42	45.65	55.03	45.65	48.75	47.20	51.12
7	UAK-15-1-2	66.42	49.30	57.86	49.30	45.00	47.15	52.51
8	UAK-15-2-8	49.25	40.95	45.10	40.95	43.75	42.35	43.73
9	UAK-15-12-15	44.75	35.95	40.35	35.95	43.00	39.48	39.91
10	UAK-15-6-3	41.17	33.35	37.26	33.35	58.75	46.05	41.66
11	UAK-15-19-7	55.34	35.85	45.59	35.85	30.50	33.18	39.38
12	UAK-15-1-7	49.50	28.30	38.90	28.30	47.00	37.65	38.28
13	UAK-15-6-7	64.50	37.80	51.15	37.80	55.25	46.53	48.84
14	UAK-15-1-4-2	58.83	37.90	48.37	37.90	59.50	48.70	48.54
15	Anjasmoro	51.42	36.10	43.76	36.10	57.00	46.55	45.16
16	Grobogan	39.08	32.45	35.77	32.45	40.00	36.23	36.00
Average		52.90	37.92	45.41	37.92	47.72	42.82	44.12

Table 8. Number of empty pod of 16 soybean genotypes in lowland and upland

No	Genotype	No of empty pod/plant						Grand average
		Upland			Lowland			
		Blitar	Pasuruan	Average	Banyuwangi	Nganjuk	Avrg	
1	UAK-15-11-2	2.58	2.00	2.29	2.00	1.75	1.88	2.08
2	UAK-15-1-6	2.25	1.25	1.75	1.25	1.17	1.21	1.48
3	UAK-15-7-1	3.58	2.00	2.79	2.00	0.92	1.46	2.13
4	UAK-15-5-1	4.08	2.00	3.04	2.00	1.17	1.59	2.31
5	UAK-15-2-1	4.84	2.75	3.79	2.75	2.17	2.46	3.13
6	UAK-15-1-4	2.09	2.50	2.29	2.50	1.17	1.84	2.06
7	UAK-15-1-2	3.83	2.50	3.17	2.50	1.58	2.04	2.61
8	UAK-15-2-8	1.42	2.05	1.73	2.05	0.58	1.32	1.52
9	UAK-15-12-15	1.50	1.75	1.62	1.75	0.92	1.34	1.48
10	UAK-15-6-3	1.83	2.00	1.92	2.00	0.58	1.29	1.61
11	UAK-15-19-7	1.25	2.00	1.63	2.00	0.42	1.21	1.42
12	UAK-15-1-7	4.00	1.75	2.88	1.75	1.92	1.84	2.36
13	UAK-15-6-7	4.42	2.50	3.46	2.50	1.33	1.92	2.69
14	UAK-15-1-4-2	4.58	2.25	3.42	2.25	2.00	2.13	2.77
15	Anjasmoro	2.17	2.25	2.21	2.25	2.17	2.21	2.21
16	Grobogan	2.08	1.50	1.79	1.50	0.83	1.17	1.48
Average		2.91	2.07	2.49	2.07	1.29	1.68	2.09

In this study, based on the performance of yield and yield components of several soybean genotypes in upland and lowland, there were several genotypes that are adaptive and capable to produce high yield in both types of land. In Brazil, Soares et al. (2015) evaluated several soybean genotypes in various seasons and recommended TMG 801 RR cultivars to be developed in the southern part of the Minas Gerais region.

In tropical agrosystems such as Indonesia, in which soybeans can be cultivated in various growing seasons, the availability of soybean varieties with optimal production in both of upland and lowland are important. In this research, two soybean genotypes, namely UAK-15-6-7 (3.01 t/ha) and UAK-15-1-4-2 (3.03 t/ha) were able to produce higher than the check varieties of Anjasmoro (2.28 t/ha) and Grobogan (2.42 t/ha). Both genotypes meet the soybean user preferences, namely early maturity and large seed size.

CONCLUSIONS

The upland and lowland have the potential for soybean development in Indonesia. Soybean genotypes UAK-15-6-7 and UAK-15-1-4-2 were identified as adaptable to both of upland and lowland, and their agronomic characteristics were in accordance with the soybean preferences in Indonesia, i.e. early maturity and large seed size. The UAK-15-11-2 was suitable to be developed in upland, whereas UAK-15-1-4 was more suitable to be developed in lowland.

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